

Deliverable D3.4

IC Guidelines and Training Models

UNITA - WP3

Co-funded by
the Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Torino, 30/06/2023

Project Acronym	UNITA
Project Title	UNITA - Universitas Montium
Document Author	WP3 Task Force
Project Coordinator	Maurizio De Tullio
Project Duration	36 Months
Deliverable No.	D3.4
Dissemination level *	PU
Work Package	WP3
Task	T3.1.4
Lead beneficiary	UNITO
Due date of deliverable	30/06/2023
Actual submission date	03/07/2023
Document version	1.0

* PU = Public; PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services); RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services); CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Agency Services)

Abstract

EN

This deliverable contains a list of syllabi which portray the extent and specialization of the intercomprehension trainings organized within the UNITA project and which may be used as guidelines for IC courses which could be implemented by any university of the UNITA alliance.

The scientific literature overview and outputs produced during the first period of the project were used to establish a starting point from which UNITA began to build new syllabi, best practices and new action-research, making a solid contribution to the theoretical and practical development of pluri/multilingual education and multilingualism in general.

All syllabi were compiled under the guidance of UNITO to facilitate alignment among partners on knowledge of IC resources and skills. After this phase, IC teaching was consolidated and partners became more aware of existing practices and tools. After sharing basic references and mapping of previous and existing IC projects, WP3 worked on best practices to be shared both internally and externally to UNITA. A UNITA framework and various syllabi for IC teaching courses aimed at different target audiences were discussed and implemented.

Starting initially with the creation of a syllabus for the training of Erasmus students, the WP3 group then focused on a syllabus for the training of non-linguistic University Lecturers and then another for the training of administrative staff of UNITA partner universities. The Erasmus course was organized entirely online, allowing interaction between students from different institutions. Courses for faculty and staff were developed in a hybrid mode, with a presential part, at each institution, and an online part in interaction with colleagues from other universities, aimed at practicing interaction and communication in IC between speakers of related languages.

Other syllabi completed the training offer aimed at the acquisition of fundamental skills and knowledge for an aware multilingual communication: a syllabus for an online IC training for intercomprehension trainers, a syllabus for a COIL project aimed at students in intercomprehension courses, and a syllabus for a Blended intensive program (BIP) project.

IT

Questo deliverable contiene una lista di sillabi che illustrano l'ampiezza e la specializzazione dei corsi di intercomprensione organizzati nell'ambito del progetto UNITA e che possono essere utilizzati come linee guida per corsi di intercomprensione che potrebbero essere implementati da qualsiasi università dell'alleanza UNITA.

La panoramica della letteratura scientifica e i risultati prodotti durante il primo periodo del progetto sono stati utilizzati per stabilire un punto di partenza da cui UNITA ha iniziato a costruire nuovi sillabi, buone pratiche e nuove esperienze di ricerca-azione, dando un solido contributo allo sviluppo teorico e pratico dell'educazione plurilingue e del multilinguismo.

Tutti i sillabi sono stati compilati sotto la guida di UNITO, per facilitare l'allineamento tra i partner sulla conoscenza delle risorse e delle competenze in materia di IC. Dopo questa fase, l'insegnamento dell'IC è stato consolidato e i partner sono diventati più consapevoli delle pratiche e degli strumenti esistenti. Dopo aver condiviso i riferimenti di base e la mappatura dei progetti IC precedenti ed esistenti, il WP3 ha lavorato sulle buone pratiche da condividere sia internamente che esternamente a UNITA. Sono stati discussi e implementati un quadro di riferimento UNITA e i sillabi per i corsi di insegnamento dell'IC rivolti a diversi target.

Partito inizialmente dalla creazione di un sillabo per la formazione degli **studenti Erasmus**, il gruppo di lavoro del WP3 si è poi concentrato su un sillabo per la formazione dei **Docenti universitari non linguisti** e poi su un altro per la formazione dello **staff amministrativo** delle Università partner di UNITA. Il corso Erasmus è stato organizzato in maniera interamente online, permettendo l'interazione tra gli studenti delle diverse istituzioni. I corsi per docenti e staff si sono sviluppati in modalità ibrida, con una parte presenziale, in ogni istituzione e una parte online in interazione con i colleghi delle altre università, finalizzata alla pratica dell'interazione e della comunicazione in IC tra parlanti di lingue affini.

Altri sillabi hanno completato l'offerta formativa dedicata all'acquisizione di strumenti per la comunicazione multilingue: un sillabo per la **formazione dei formatori** di intercomprensione, un sillabo per un **progetto COIL** rivolto a studenti dei corsi di intercomprensione e un sillabo per un progetto di **Blended intensive programme (BIP)**.

FR

Ce document contient une liste de syllabus qui décrivent l'étendue et la spécialisation des formations à l'intercompréhension organisées dans le cadre du projet UNITA et qui peuvent être utilisés comme lignes directrices pour les cours d'intercompréhension qui pourraient être mis en œuvre par n'importe quelle université de l'alliance UNITA.

L'aperçu de la littérature scientifique et les résultats obtenus au cours de la première période du projet ont été utilisés pour établir un point de départ à partir duquel UNITA a commencé à élaborer de nouveaux programmes, de meilleures pratiques et de nouvelles recherches-actions, apportant ainsi une solide contribution au développement théorique et pratique de l'éducation pluri/multilingue et du multilinguisme en général.

Tous les programmes ont été compilés sous la direction d'UNITO afin de faciliter l'alignement entre les partenaires sur la connaissance des ressources et des compétences en matière d'éducation interculturelle. Après cette phase, l'enseignement de l'IC a été consolidé et les partenaires sont devenus plus conscients des pratiques et des outils existants. Après avoir partagé des références de base et dressé la carte des projets d'IC antérieurs et existants, le WP3 a travaillé sur les bonnes pratiques à partager à l'intérieur et à l'extérieur d'UNITA. Un cadre UNITA et des syllabus pour les cours de CI destinés à différents groupes cibles ont été discutés et mis en œuvre.

Le groupe de travail WP3 a commencé par créer un syllabus pour la formation des étudiants Erasmus, puis s'est concentré sur un syllabus pour la formation des professeurs d'université non linguistes et ensuite sur un autre pour la formation du personnel administratif des universités partenaires de l'UNITA. Le cours Erasmus a été organisé entièrement en ligne, ce qui a permis une interaction entre les étudiants des différentes institutions. Les cours destinés aux enseignants et au personnel ont été élaborés selon un mode hybride, avec une partie en présentiel dans chaque établissement et une partie en ligne en interaction avec des collègues d'autres universités, dans le but de pratiquer l'interaction et la communication dans le domaine de l'IC entre des locuteurs de langues apparentées.

D'autres syllabus ont complété l'offre de formation dédiée à l'acquisition d'outils de communication multilingue : un syllabus pour la formation de formateurs en intercompréhension, un syllabus pour un projet COIL destiné aux étudiants des cours d'intercompréhension et un syllabus pour un projet Blended Intensive Programme (BIP).

ES

Este informe contiene una lista de programas de estudios que reflejan el alcance y la especialización de las formaciones en intercomprensión organizadas en el marco del proyecto UNITA y que pueden utilizarse como directrices para los cursos de CI que podría impartir cualquier universidad de la alianza UNITA.

La visión general de la literatura científica y los resultados obtenidos durante el primer período del proyecto se utilizaron para establecer un punto de partida a partir del cual UNITA comenzó a construir nuevos planes de estudio, buenas prácticas y nuevas investigaciones-acción, haciendo una sólida contribución al desarrollo teórico y práctico de la educación pluri/multilingüe y del multilingüismo en general.

Todos los programas de estudios se elaboraron bajo la dirección de UNITO para facilitar la armonización entre los socios en cuanto al conocimiento de los recursos y las competencias de la IC. Tras esta fase, la enseñanza de la IC se consolidó y los socios adquirieron un mayor conocimiento de las prácticas y herramientas existentes. Tras compartir las referencias básicas y realizar un mapeo de los proyectos de IC anteriores y existentes, el WP3 trabajó en las buenas prácticas para compartirlas tanto dentro como fuera de UNITA. Se debatieron y pusieron en práctica un marco UNITA y programas de estudios para cursos de enseñanza de la IC dirigidos a diferentes grupos objetivo.

Comenzando inicialmente con la creación de un programa para la formación de estudiantes Erasmus, el grupo de trabajo del WP3 se centró después en un plan de estudios para la formación de profesores universitarios no lingüistas y, posteriormente, en otro para la formación del personal administrativo de las universidades socias de UNITA. El curso Erasmus se organizó íntegramente en línea, lo que permitió la interacción entre estudiantes de las distintas instituciones. Los cursos para profesores y

personal administrativo se desarrollaron en modalidad híbrida, con una parte presencial en cada institución y otra en línea en interacción con colegas de otras universidades, destinada a practicar la interacción y comunicación en IC entre hablantes de lenguas afines.

Otros planes de estudios completaron la oferta formativa dedicada a la adquisición de herramientas para la comunicación multilingüe: un curso para la formación de formadores en intercomprensión, un curso para un proyecto COIL dirigido a estudiantes de cursos de intercomprensión y un curso para el Programa Intensivo Semipresencial (BIP).

PT

Este documento contém uma lista de programas de estudo que retratam a extensão e a especialização das formações em intercompreensão organizadas no âmbito do projeto UNITA e que podem ser utilizados como diretrizes para cursos de CI que podem ser implementados por qualquer universidade da aliança UNITA.

A síntese da literatura científica e os resultados produzidos durante o primeiro período do projeto foram utilizados para estabelecer um ponto de partida a partir do qual a UNITA começou a construir novos programas de estudo, melhores práticas e nova investigação-ação, dando um contributo sólido para o desenvolvimento teórico e prático da educação pluri/multilingue e do multilinguismo em geral.

Todos os programas de estudo foram compilados sob a orientação da UNITA para facilitar o alinhamento entre os parceiros no conhecimento dos recursos e competências de IC. Após esta fase, o ensino da IC foi consolidado e os parceiros ficaram mais conscientes das práticas e ferramentas existentes. Depois de partilhar referências básicas e mapear projectos de IC anteriores e existentes, o WP3 trabalhou em boas práticas a serem partilhadas dentro e fora da UNITA. Foram discutidos e implementados um quadro e programas da UNITA para cursos de ensino de IC destinados a diferentes grupos-alvo.

Começando inicialmente com a criação de um programa de estudos para a formação de estudantes Erasmus, o grupo de trabalho do WP3 concentrou-se depois num programa de estudos para a formação de professores universitários não linguistas e, em seguida, num outro para a formação de pessoal administrativo das universidades parceiras da UNITA. O curso Erasmus foi organizado inteiramente em linha, permitindo a interação entre os estudantes das diferentes instituições. Os cursos para docentes e funcionários foram desenvolvidos numa modalidade híbrida, com uma parte presencial em cada instituição e uma parte em linha em interação com colegas de outras universidades, com o objetivo de praticar a interação e a comunicação em IC entre falantes de línguas afins.

Outros programas completaram a oferta de formação dedicada à aquisição de ferramentas para a comunicação multilingue: um programa para a formação de formadores de intercompreensão, um

programa para um projeto COIL destinado a estudantes de cursos de intercompreensão e um programa para um projeto de Programa Intensivo Combinado (BIP).

Summary

Abstract	1
Summary	6
1. IC courses syllabuses for students	7
1.1. IC for Erasmus students course syllabus (30hrs)	7
1.2. UCIL-IC for students of foreign languages and non-linguists	7
2. IC courses syllabuses for teachers, staff and trainers	8
2.1. IC for Teachers course syllabus (15hrs)	8
2.2. IC for Staff course syllabus (18hrs)	10
2.3. IC for Trainers course syllabus (50hrs)	11
3. Blended Intensive Programs for IC	12
4. An open access course: <i>Elementi di IC</i> on Start@UNITO	13

1. IC courses syllabuses for students

1.1. IC for Erasmus students course syllabus (30hrs)

The Erasmus course is open to all UNITA alliance students who have won a mobility scholarship. It has a duration of thirty hours which are divided into eighteen hours of distance learning lectures, carried out in synchronous mode and twelve hours of activities in asynchronous mode.

The course is divided into four modules as follows:

1. Fundamental principles of IC
2. IC and everyday life
3. IC and universities
4. IC and specialised languages.

The first module includes a theoretical introduction and familiarisation activities with IC and interaction in multilingual contexts. Modules two, three and four involve receptive IC activities, oral and written interactive IC. At the end of each lesson, students are asked to write a compilative logbook constructed on a scale of one to five in which they assess their their progression in the acquisition of skills and in which they indicate the presence or absence of difficulties in the lectures.

1.2. UCIL-IC for students of foreign languages and non-linguists

Partners involved

UNITO + UPPA + USMB + UVT

Context

Each of the above-mentioned partners organises 'local' intercomprehension courses with a large majority of students being native speakers of the country and thus of the same mother tongue. Consequently, local courses offer little linguistic and cultural 'variety' (if we exclude regional languages). For this reason, we decided to bring all students together in a large international group, so that they could experience the practice of intercomprehension through telecollaboration and collaborative work in multilingual teams.

Articulation of the COIL project

Based on the know-how of the "Gala-Miriadi" partnership, the activities are structured on the basis of a scenario involving:

- Local group work: the course takes place in each partner's institution.
- International teamwork: an open course on Moodle with a forum.
- Multilingual group work: tasks to be carried out in small multilingual groups.

Detailed syllabus

The module implies:

- 8-12 weeks of local IC courses and activities (depending on the calendar of each university).
- 6 weeks of collaborative (asynchronous) written activities, on the UNITA Moodle forum, structured on the basis of 4 phases (MIRIADI scenario) and including a final collaborative task.
- 3 videoconference meetings of 30 minutes each for each working group, independently managed and recorded, for the organization of the work. Depending on the number of groups, each working group is co-supervised by an "IC expert".
- If possible: presentation of the group work in plenary, in the presence of the international group. Otherwise: video-presentations of each groupwork.

Languages of communication

Learners' mother tongues + other possible bridging languages

Final outputs

The students realize various activities, games, presentations on

Weaknesses

Spanish and Portuguese language learners are currently missing.

2. IC courses syllabuses for teachers, staff and trainers

2.1. IC for Teachers course syllabus (15hrs)

General organization

1. Presentation (1h) - online -
2. IC principles (2h) - asynchronous task
3. Written IC and interproduction strategies (4h) - on site
4. Oral IC and interproduction strategies (3h) - online
5. Microteaching (3h) - asynchronous + task
6. Good practice feedback (2h) - online

Detailed syllabus

1.PRESENTATION (1h) - SYNCHRONOUS, ONLINE

First meeting and course presentation (1h, SYNCHRONOUS, online; all teachers (one slide each in another language)

1. general presentations by teachers (tour de table)
2. Jeu des questions/réponses plurilingues
3. course presentation
 - a. contents and dates (RO 1 with slides in ITA) -

- b. tasks and objectives (FR with 1 slide in PT) -
 - c. moodle functioning (PT with 1 slide in ES) -
- => two minutes between each presentation to collect questions or doubts in the chat room

TASK 1: Write presentations on the forum and personalize your profile.

2. IC PRINCIPLES (2h) - ASYNCHRONOUS

On the forum: interactions for questions about the course, IC questions, etc.

3. WRITTEN INTERCOMPREHENSION (4h) - ON SITE

=> focus on comprehension and production

1. Separated into two lessons (2hrs each) : 2h theory and 2h work on the simplification task
2. On Forum
 - by the end of the week DELIVERY TASK 2 SIMPLIFICATION (after examples)
 - interaction to comment => before the oral course

TASK 2: Simplify a text and post it on the forum, comment on other people's texts (what I understood, what I didn't understand).

4. ORAL IC AND INTERPRODUCTION (3h) - SYNCHRONOUS, ONLINE

=> return on simplification in the forum (30 minutes)

=> VIDEO: example of courses (30 minutes)

A. Video of a lesson to watch and comment (1h)

- Show a video;
- In groups of 2: what worked and what didn't?
- Then joint reflection (feedback)

B. Theory: oral comprehension and interaction (1h)

- Particularities of oral comprehension (phonetics)
- VIDEO Teletandem and UCIL-IC

C. In groups: DOs and DON'Ts

- Which international words did we use? Which are pan-romance?

5. MICROTEACHING (3h) - ASYNCHRONOUS + TASK

TASK 3: Recording of a lesson in which the teacher uses IC strategies in order to be understood by non-native students.

6. FEEDBACK AND GOOD PRACTICE (2h) - SYNCHRONOUS, ONLINE

1. Brainstorming (WOOCLAP) Questions: Easy/ Difficult - Which aspect did they favour most in creating the video? Meanwhile: Those who did not create the video should go and watch 2 videos: I will send them to you on whatsapp.

2. Feedback from the teachers and general remarks
3. Creation of the “Decalogue of good practices in IC” for a non-linguistic teacher (5 min to do it individually then groupwork)
4. Back to plenary: create a unique decalogue for this course.

2.2. IC for Staff course syllabus (18hrs)

Platforms: Moodle UNITA and Start@UNITO.

General organization

1. Module 1: introduction do IC and autonomous learning of IC theories and principles.
2. Module 2: written and oral IC (focus on strategies)
3. Module 3: interacting in IC (focus on practice and peer to peer interaction)

Detailed syllabus

MODULE 1: 6 hours

- On site course (2hrs): general introduction to IC
- Online course of IC - autonomous (Start UNITO) (4hrs)

MODULE 2: 6 hours

- Online course of IC (1h), international group:
Introduction with all the students and teachers. Presentations and plurilingual games in breakout rooms.
- On site course (2hrs):
Written and oral “interproduction” + mail writing: problems & solutions
- TASK (30 minutes): write an email concerning a “staff” subject (on forums)
- Online course of IC (2hrs), international group:
Online interactions + breakout rooms (getting started / Ice breaking)
in small groups → negotiate the simplification of professional texts, see what works, what doesn't (table to fill in). Feedback on transparency/opacity in plenum
Table: email lexicon in all languages
Activities: Feedbacks on the emails posted: useful simplifications, suggestions, etc.
- TASK (30 minutes): Produce a 3-minute video in which they present their profession.

MODULE 3: 6 hours

- On site course (2hrs): observation and analysis of some videos of interactions/ meetings of staff groups.

- TASK: Role play. Interaction between 2 foreign partners: 30 minutes of interactions and 30 minutes of reflections on the strategies employed to communicate (with guided questions).
- Online course of IC (2hrs): with turn-taking and note-taking. Observations on the teletandem activities. Role play in breakout rooms: organization of a staff week.
- FINAL TASK (1h): plan of the staff week.

2.3. IC for Trainers course syllabus (50hrs)

Within the framework of the European alliance "UNITA - Universitas Montium", the Language Center of the University of Turin organises a training course to acquire teaching skills in intercomprehension. It is aimed at teachers of Romance languages and university teachers of Romance languages and students interested in language teaching. At the end of the course an Open Badge of IC Teacher Training is issued.

General organization

1. Part 1: Introductory course on the basics of CI (10 hours)
2. Part 2: Practical IC course: on the student's side (15 hours)
3. Part 3: Presentation and testing of IC teaching materials (15 hours)
4. Part 4: Final paper (10 hours)

Detailed syllabus

1. Brief introduction to intercomprehension (4hrs):

- IC origins, projects and teaching perspectives
- The IC teacher: a guide and a facilitator
- Receptive and interactive IC
- Pluralistic resources for communication: the language biography tool
- IC in UNITA

2. Interaction in intercomprehension:

Eurom + MIRIADI and IOTT (synchronous online lessons, synchronous and asynchronous teletandem, task-based activities):

- Receptive IC (text approach and strategies in place)
- Interactive CI and task-based learning
- Interactional learning in CI, a double mise en abyme

3. FEEDBACK and (self-)observation

- Top-down/bottom-up intercomprehension strategies for reading and listening
- Oral intercomprehension and observation of strategies in interactive IC

4. Materials and microteaching

- IC frameworks (Refic, EVALIC)
- Materials and activities → experimentation

5. Final work (10 hours)

3. Blended Intensive Programs for IC

General organization

These Blended Intensive Programs are divided into 3 modules:

1. Virtual autonomous activities
2. Online lessons
3. Intensive IC week – on site

Detailed syllabus

The virtual activities are carried out autonomously by the students and are based on the plurilingual online course “Elementi di Intercomprensione”, freely available on the Start@unito platform.

A first online lesson is organized to explain the syllabus of the course, its goals and requirements. Then, the two other lessons are distributed over 3 different week in order to scaffold the student’s acquisition of IC strategies.

During the intensive week students consolidate knowledge and skills developed during the virtual part of the BIP; furthermore, they will focus on the techniques and principles of IC in Language for Specific Purposes (LSP) contexts, participating to content classes (using video recordings, simulations, or actual classes depending on availability). The choice of the LSPs to be dealt with will also be based on the profile of the students enrolled in the program.

time/day	MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI
9.30-10.00	Welcoming session	IC warm up	IC warm up	IC warm up	IC warm up
10.00-11.15	IC back to basics	IC task-based activity (general)	IC task-based activity (general)	IC task-based activity (LSP)	IC task-based activity (LSP)

time/day	MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI
11.00-11.45	IC back to basics	IC and LSP reading	IC and LSP reading	IC and LSP reading	IC and LSP reading
11.45-12.30	IC back to basics	IC and LSP strategies	IC and LSP strategies	IC and LSP strategies	IC and LSP strategies
	break	break	break	break	break
14.30-16.00	Task-based activity (general)	LSP class Science + tasks	LSP class Philosophy + tasks	LSP class Mathematics + tasks	LSP class Architecture + tasks
16.00-16.30	feedback	feedback	feedback	feedback	feedback
14.30-16.00	Task-based activity (general)	LSP class Science + tasks	LSP class Philosophy + tasks	LSP class Mathematics + tasks	LSP class Architecture + tasks
16.00-16.30	feedback	feedback	feedback	feedback	feedback

4. An open access course: *Elementi di IC* on Start@UNITO

Elementi di IC is a self-study online course aimed at giving an insight into what IC is and the basic principles of the discipline and divided into 3 modules:

- Introduction to IC general strategies
- Written IC strategies
- Oral IC strategies

It is a course that can be chosen either by UNITA students who can add it to their university curriculum or by teachers, staff members and BIP students who use it as blended introduction to the in-presence classes.

This course gives students, teachers and staff who complete it and pass the final test 3 ECTS.